

Is it possible that combined alpha-tocopherol and CoQ10 can combat testicular injury induced by arsenic

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SUMMARY

Arsenic emerges as a significant public health issue. Therefore, it makes sense to identify appropriate compounds to alleviate arsenic toxicity. Alpha-tocopherol and Coenzyme Q10 were tested for their ability to avert arsenic effects. 30 mice were recruited and divided into 5 groups, each consisting of six animals. The mice in these 5 groups were exposed to drinking water (136 parts per million of arsenic). The whole duration was 30 days. The control group received only free distilled water. The arsenic (As) group was treated with water containing arsenic. (As+ α -tocopherol) group received arsenic and alpha-tocopherol (50 mg/kg bw). The As+CoQ10 group was treated with arsenic and CoQ10 (10 mg/kg b.wt.), while the As+ α -tocopherol+CoQ10 group was treated with arsenic and a combination of both. According to biochemical data, the group exposed to arsenic had significantly lower levels of reduced glutathione, total thiol, and superoxide dismutase than the control group, while its level of lipid peroxidation was higher. Antioxidant treatment miti-

gated these changes. Alpha-tocopherol, CoQ10, and a combination of these substances reduce the changes caused by arsenic, which causes DNA damage in blood cells by exhibiting a significantly lower head DNA percentage and a higher tail DNA percentage, tail length, and tail moment. In conclusion, Alpha-tocopherol and CoQ10 together is more effective than using these antioxidants separately against arsenic.

Key words: Alpha-tocopherol – Coenzyme Q10 – Arsenic – Oxidative stress – DNA damage

INTRODUCTION

Prolonged exposure to arsenic through tainted food and drinking water can cause major health problems, such as skin lesions and cancer. It is also linked to diabetes and cardiovascular diseases. Additionally, exposure during pregnancy and the early years of life has been connected to poor cognitive development and higher rates of young adult mortality. Chronic exposure to arsenic affects the central and peripheral nervous systems,

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leading to depression, memory problems, difficulty-solving problems, and impaired body coordination, as noted by Sharma and Kumar (2019) and Raeeszadeh et al. (2021).

Over 140 million people use drinking water that contains arsenic at levels higher than the WHO's recommended provisional value of 10 µg/L worldwide (Akhigbe et al., 2024). According to Wang et al., arsenic is a reproductive toxin that causes malformations in humans and animals, particularly neural tube defects (Li et al., 2023a). Higher doses of inorganic arsenic during the early stages of pregnancy were linked to malformations in mice (Ortiz-Garcia et al., 2023). According to a study, inorganic arsenic causes disruptions in steroidogenesis (Adeogun et al., 2024), decreases in testosterone and gonadotrophins, and variations in spermatogenesis (Li et al., 2023b). Male mice exposed to arsenic also showed changes in androgenic activity, decreased sperm count, motility, and hormonal imbalances (Li et al., 2023b). Arsenic has also been linked to cell cycle disruption, DNA repair inhibition, and ubiquitin (a protein) dysregulation, all of which increase DNA damage (Wang et al., 2023).

Researchers tested a variety of natural and synthetic substances against arsenic's toxicity as medicinal plants and natural compounds (Kumar et al., 2024) that demonstrated notable protection against arsenic toxicity, and according to review of data on medicinal plants and natural compounds against arsenic toxicity (Paul et al., 2023) that suggested a respectable findings. However, an appropriate substance is still required to prevent toxicity caused by arsenic. In order to test against arsenic-induced testicular oxidative stress and DNA damage in mice, alpha-tocopherol (α-tocopherol) and Coenzyme Q10 (CoQ10) were combined.

Alpha-tocopherol is the most powerful of the lipid-soluble vitamin E family. It has been shown to function as an antioxidant in cells, inhibiting the growth of lipid peroxidation in the plasma membrane and maintaining membrane integrity (Ziamajidi et al., 2023). The protective qualities of α-tocopherol against different toxicants have been evaluated in a few studies (Prastiya et al., 2024, de Oliveira et al., 2023).

According to reports, CoQ10 functions as a strong antioxidant, prevents lipid peroxidation from starting and spreading in cellular bio-membranes, and aids in α-tocopherol renewal, also CoQ10 successfully shields mice's testicles from damage brought on by magnetic field radiation (Gardela et al., 2023).

It has been demonstrated that α-tocopherol and CoQ10 are both effective in preventing cadmium-induced testicular toxicity in mice (Sitek and Kozłowska, 2022). We recently found that α-tocopherol and CoQ10 help protect mice's brains from the harmful effects of arsenic (Ali et al., 2022).

Therefore, the purpose of this study was to assess the protective effects of α-tocopherol and CoQ10, either separately or in combination, against arsenic-induced oxidative stress and DNA damage in mice.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Ethical approval

The study was conducted after approval by the Medical Research Ethics Committee of the Faculty of Medicine, Ain Shams University, Cairo, Egypt (MS 89/2023).

Chemicals

Sigma Aldrich (St. Louis, USA) provided the α-tocopherol, CoQ10, and sodium meta-arsenite.

Animals

From the animal house, adult albino mice (6-8 weeks; 22±3 g), which were maintained in accordance with the guidelines set by the ethics committee. In the Animal House facility, animals were acclimated for approximately a week. The mice were housed in polypropylene cages with regulated humidity, temperature, and light and dark cycles (12 hours each).

Experimental design

30 mice were recruited divided into 5 groups each consisting of six animals in the experimental plan. The groups were distributed as follows:

(Control): Control group received only free distilled water.

(As): Arsenic group received arsenic (at a dose of 136 ppm) in distilled water.

(As + α -tocopherol): Arsenic (at a dose of 136 ppm) and α -tocopherol in distilled water.

(As + CoQ10): Arsenic (at a dose of 136 ppm) and CoQ10 in distilled water.

(As+ α -tocopherol+CoQ10): Arsenic (at a dose of 136 ppm) and both α -tocopherol and CoQ10 in distilled water.

The whole duration for the treatment is 30 days

Preparing the dose and the exposure method

Dosage of Arsenic: Double-distilled water was used to dissolve sodium meta-arsenite (NaAsO₂). To prevent oxidation, a dose of arsenic (136 ppm) was prepared every other day by dissolving a suitable amount of arsenic in double-distilled water and administered to the mice (Sharma et al., 2018). [The daily dose is 1/3 of LD 50 (acute) reported dose of arsenic] (Sharma et al., 2018).

Antioxidant Dosage: The antioxidants α -tocopherol (50 mg/kg b.wt.) (Rajak et al., 2022) and CoQ10 (10 mg/kg b.wt.) (Abd-Elhakim et al., 2023) were dissolved in 1% aqueous tween-80 after being separately weighed. Three groups of mice were given antioxidants (α -tocopherol and CoQ10 separately and in combination) intraperitoneally every day for 30 days after being treated with arsenic.

Body and Testis weight

Body weight was measured every day throughout the course of treatment to track any changes. Following the planned treatment, animals were put to sleep with CO₂ gas in a glass chamber and sacrificed after blood was drawn through the retro-orbital sinus for DNA damage analysis using the comet assay. The testes were removed, cleaned, blotted, and weighed.

Estimates of Oxidative Stress levels

To measure the following biochemical parameters, testes were homogenized in phosphate buffer (0.1 M; pH-7) with 0.5% triton X-100, centrifuged

at 5000 rpm at 4°C (Sigma 3-18K, Germany), and the supernatant was extracted in various aliquots.

Lipid Peroxidation (LPO)

Malondialdehyde (MDA) was measured in testes tissue homogenate as a lipid peroxidation index depending on the reaction with thiobarbituric acid-reactive substances. Spectrophotometrically has a maximum absorption peak at 532 nm using Elabscience® Malondialdehyde (MDA) Colorimetric Assay Kit (TBA Method) according to the manual instructions (Catalog No:E-BC-K025-S) (Mustafa, 2021). MDA in the catabolite of lipid peroxide can react with thiobarbituric acid (TBA) and produce red compound, which has a maximum absorption peak at 532 nm.

Reduced glutathione (GSH): Reduced Glutathione (GSH) can react with Dinitrobenzoic acid (DNTB) to form a yellow complex, which can be detected by colorimetric assay at 405 nm, and calculate the reduced GSH content indirectly using Colorimetric Assay Kit, according to the manual instructions (Catalog No:E-BC-K030-M) (Mustafa, 2023).

Total thiol (TT): The detection principle depends on whether this Sulfhydryl compounds react with 5,5'-dithiobis (2-nitrobenzoic acid) under neutral or alkaline conditions to produce a yellow product which has a maximum absorption peak at 412 nm. Measure the OD value and calculate the total mercapto content indirectly using Elabscience® Total Sulfhydryl Group / Total Thiol (-SH) Colorimetric Assay Kit, according to the manual instructions (Catalog No: E-BC-K265-M) (Hafizoglu et al., 2024).

Antioxidant enzyme activity

Superoxide dismutase (SOD): The detection principle depends on the superoxide anion free radical (O₂⁻), which can be produced by xanthine and xanthine oxidase reaction system; O₂⁻ oxidize hydroxylamine to form nitrite; it turns to purple under the reaction of developer. When the measured samples contain SOD, the SOD can specifically inhibit superoxide anion free radical (O₂⁻). The inhibitory effect of SOD can reduce the formation of nitrite; the absorbance value of

sample tube is lower than control tube. Calculate the SOD of samples according to the computational formula using Total Superoxide Dismutase (T-SOD) Activity Assay Kit according to the manual instructions (Hydroxylamine Method) (Catalog No: E-BC-K019-S) (Mustafa, 2021).

Total protein level: The detection principle depends on whether the Coomassie brilliant blue G-250 is red under the free state and has the maximum absorbance at 465 nm. When the Coomassie brilliant blue G-250 is combined with protein, the compound will have the maximum at 595 nm. The absorbance value is directly proportional to the protein content, so the concentration of total protein can be calculated directly by measuring the OD value at 595 nm using Elabscience® Bradford Protein Colorimetric Kit according to manufacturer (Catalog No: E-BC-K168-M) (Nwizugbo et al., 2023).

DNA Damage: The comet assay, also referred to as Single Cell Gel Electrophoresis (SCGE), is a simple method for measuring deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA) strand breaks in eukaryotic cells. Cells embedded in agarose on a microscope slide are lysed with detergent and high salt to form nucleoids containing supercoiled loops of DNA linked to the nuclear matrix. The Comet assay software project (CASP software) was used for the observation and data analysis of the comet assay using fluorescence microscopy (Leica, Germany). Each animal had at least 100 cells scored to determine whether DNA damage had occurred (Sani et al., 2024).

Statistical analysis

The data were given as mean and standard deviation. To establish the significance of the mean between the groups, one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used, followed by a Bonferroni post hoc test (SPSS 28). P-values of less than 0.05 were considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

Change in body and testis weights

The group exposed to arsenic had a statistically significant lower mean body weight than the control group. Compared to the group treated solely with arsenic, the body weight was higher in the three antioxidant-protected groups (α -tocopherol, CoQ10, and their combination). However, compared to the group that was only treated with arsenic, the weight gain was statistically significantly higher in the group that was protected by combined α -tocopherol + CoQ10 (Fig. 1). Compared to the control group, the arsenic-exposed group showed a decrease in testis weight. However, compared to the group that was only treated with arsenic, the testis weight was higher in all three antioxidant-protected groups. When compared to the antioxidant-protected group (α -tocopherol and CoQ10), it was more prominent in combined α -tocopherol + CoQ10 (Fig. 1). However, the changes in testis weight observed in the treated groups were not statistically significant.

Fig 1.- Body weight changes between the different groups (left). $p < 0.05$ *compared to arsenic treated group; **compared to control group. Testis weight changes between the different groups (right).

Change in LPO level: Malondialdehyde (MDA)

The group that received arsenic treatment had a significantly higher level of MDA than the control group. In contrast to the arsenic-treated group, the antioxidant-protected groups had lower MDA levels. In comparison to the arsenic-treated group, the CoQ10 and combined α -tocopherol and CoQ10-treated groups had significantly lower levels of MDA (Fig. 2). In contrast, the α -tocopherol-protected group's MDA level was likewise lower than that of the arsenic-exposed group, although

the difference was not statistically significant.

Change in GSH level

Compared to the control group, the arsenic-toxicated group's GSH level was significantly lower. All antioxidant groups had higher GSH levels than the arsenic-treated group. In contrast to the group exposed to arsenic, the antioxidant-protected group's GSH levels were statistically significantly higher (Fig. 3). However, there were negligible differences between the antioxidant-protected groups.

Fig 2.- MDA level between the different groups. $p < 0.05$ *compared to arsenic treated group; **compared to control group.

Fig 3.- GSH level between the different groups. $p < 0.05$ *compared to arsenic treated group; **compared to control group.

Change in total thiol level

The arsenic-treated group's total thiol level was found to be lower (statistically significant) than the control groups. In contrast to the arsenic-exposed groups, thiol levels were higher in all three antioxidant-protected groups. Compared to groups exposed to arsenic, the antioxidant-protected group's thiol level was noticeably higher (Fig. 4).

Change in Superoxide dismutase activity:

While SOD activity was higher in all three antioxidant-protected groups compared to the arsenic-exposed group, which was statistically significantly higher in the combination of antioxidant-protected groups, it was significantly lower in the arsenic-exposed group when compared to the control group (Fig. 5).

Change in protein level

The group exposed to arsenic had a noticeably lower amount of protein in their testicular tissues than the control group. The antioxidant-treated groups had a higher level of total protein than the arsenic-treated group, and the CoQ10 group and combined α -tocopherol and CoQ10-protected group had a significantly higher level of total protein than the arsenic-exposed group (Fig. 6).

DNA damage by single cell gel electrophoresis assay

After 30 days of exposure to 136 ppm arsenic, the percentage of head DNA decreased significantly compared to the control group. Compared to the group treated solely with arsenic, the antioxidant-treated group experienced a smaller decrease in the percentage of head DNA. While the tail DNA percentage in the antioxidant-treated group was lower than in the arsenic-treated group, the tail DNA percentage was statistically significantly higher in the arsenic-treated group compared to the control group. In comparison to the control group, the arsenic-treated group exhibited higher tail moment and olive tail moment. In contrast to the arsenic-treated group, the antioxidant (α -tocopherol, CoQ10, and the combination)-treated group had lower tail moments. Both antioxidants and their combination partially prevented the DNA damage caused by arsenic, but the differences were not statistically significant (Fig. 7).

DISCUSSION

Chronic exposure to arsenic results in toxic damage for various organ systems and is a lethal metalloid present in the environment. Data indicates that arsenic exposure leads to oxidative stress in the testes of treated mice, as reflected

Fig 4.- Total thiol level between the different groups. $p < 0.05$ *compared to arsenic treated group; **compared to control.

Fig 5.- SOD activity between the different groups. $p < 0.05$ *compared to arsenic treated group; **compared to control.

Fig 6.- Protein level between the different groups. $p < 0.05$ *compared to arsenic treated group; **compared to control.

by elevated levels of LPO and reduced concentrations of GSH, TT, and protein, it also results in decreased body and testicular weights.

Previous studies found that exposure to arsenic diminished testicular weights and epididymal sperm counts (Li et al., 2023a). In experimental scenarios, long-term arsenic exposure has been associated with weight loss (Couto-Santos et al., 2021; Souza et al., 2023). Moreover, other researchers demonstrated a negative correlation between arsenic consumption and body mass index (BMI) (Abuawad et al., 2021), noting an increased prevalence of underweight individuals, alongside a greater incidence of skin manifesta-

tions compared to individuals with normal weight (Gribble et al., 2013; Maharjan et al., 2007).

Recently, it has been found that arsenite reduced sperm count and disrupted testicular structure (Machado-Neves, 2022). It has also been observed that arsenite raised levels of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and malondialdehyde in the testes (Hasanuzzaman et al., 2023), while significantly lowering the activity of glutathione and total superoxide dismutase (Mishra et al., 2022).

Furthermore, arsenic has been reported to elevate lipid peroxidation levels and inflict DNA damage via reactive oxygen species (Nahar et al., 2022; Tsai et al., 2021). This study also corrob-

Fig 7.- DNA damage in blood lymphocytes of different groups. * $p < 0.05$ compared to control.

orated the idea that arsenic exposure induces oxidative stress in testicular tissues through increased MDA levels and decreased SOD, GSH, and total thiol concentrations. As previously reported by Guvvala et al., mice treated with arsenic exhibited heightened arsenic accumulation, protein carbonylation, and lipid peroxidation, linked to alterations in testicular SOD, GST, and CAT activities (Akhigbe et al., 2024; Guvvala et al., 2016).

It has been concluded that arsenic acts as a testicular toxin, inducing oxidative stress in the testicular microenvironment which compromises semen quality (Rao et al., 2024). The compromised antioxidant defense system resulting from oxidative stress is a primary factor behind the toxicity associated with arsenic, potentially leading

to infertility (Wu et al., 2021). Analysis revealed lower head DNA percentages and increased levels of tail DNA, tail length, and tail moment, indicating that arsenic inflicts DNA damage in the blood cells. Prior investigations by Guillamet et al. found that specific compounds of inorganic arsenic (sodium arsenite and sodium arsenate) and organic arsenic (tetramethyl-arsonium iodide and tetraphenyl-arsonium chloride) could enhance tail moment, a metric for genotoxicity (Guillamet et al., 2004; Benhusein et al., 2021). It has also been noted that genotoxicity was typically observed at elevated arsenic 30 doses (Ozturk et al., 2022).

Furthermore, a study involving human blood samples from arsenic-contaminated groundwater areas indicated heightened DNA damage,

increased lipid peroxidation, and elevated ROS levels, coupled with reduced antioxidant levels (Mahadik et al., 2024). The intervention of curcumin led to a decrease in DNA damage, a delay in ROS and lipid peroxidation generation, and an increase in antioxidant levels, suggesting that curcumin may offer protective benefits against arsenic-induced DNA damage (Rahaman et al., 2020).

The present findings indicated that combining α -tocopherol with CoQ10 was more effective in preventing oxidative stress in testicular tissues than either substance alone, indicating a synergistic effect of these antioxidants; this aligns with previous studies (Mahmoudi et al., 2025; Nemeč Svete et al., 2021). It has been discovered that CoQ10 and α -tocopherol protect rat testicular tissues from oxidative stressors related to cadmium (Abd-Elhakim et al., 2024). Moreover, study reported that CoQ10 shields rat testes from arsenic-induced toxicity (Eid et al., 2023). It has been found that Arsenic-exposed mice showed lower levels of testicular glutathione and higher levels of protein carbonyl, indicating oxidative damage to tissue proteins (Tripathi et al., 2022).

In the current study, a decrease in glutathione levels due to arsenic exposure was also recorded. Harmful effects of sodium arsenite on male reproductive systems was studied and how vitamin E alleviates these effects (Ortega-Morales et al., 2023). Vitamin E alleviated the adverse impacts of sodium arsenite regarding sperm count and tubule diameters (Ortega-Morales et al., 2023). Additionally, authors reported that curcumin mitigated the negative consequences of sodium arsenite on sperm parameters in adult mice (Akhter et al., 2024). Moreover, rats subjected to arsenic displayed significantly elevated levels of LPO and diminished antioxidant levels and enzyme activities (Garla et al., 2021). Other authors agreed with our findings in the current study that co-administration of CoQ10 and α -tocopherol reversed the negative consequences of arsenic (Rachamalla et al., 2022).

Earlier research indicated that enriching cells with Coenzyme Q10 prevents DNA damage and accelerates repair kinetics, whereas exposing lymphocytes to oxidizing agents elevates DNA damage (Wani and Shadab, 2021). This may relate

to the well-known antioxidant properties of Coenzyme Q10 (Mahmoudi et al., 2025).

CONCLUSION

The existing evidence, along with findings from the current study, supports the hypothesis that arsenic exposure leads to DNA damage in mouse blood cells and oxidative stress in the testes, both of which can be somewhat countered by antioxidants. Considering the significant synergistic effects of α -tocopherol and CoQ10 observed in this study, further exploration into the role of antioxidants, particularly α -tocopherol or its combination with CoQ10, in clinical applications may be warranted.

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